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Effects of Reheating Time on the Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of a Medium Manganese Steel for Hot Stamping Application

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Abstract

Advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) are continuously evolving to meet the demands from the automotive industry for improved environmental sustainability and occupant safety. Medium manganese steels (MMnS), due to the complex microstructure consisting of ferrite (α)/martensite (α') matrices with significant retained austenite (γ) fractions ($>10\%$) are future candidate for automotive components requiring high energy absorption and anti-intrusion performance. Moreover, the manganese content also facilitates warm forming at reduced temperatures, compatible with Zn-based corrosion-resistant coatings—addressing long-standing challenges like liquid metal embrittlement and microcracking in Zn-coated hot stamping steels. In this work, the effect of the reheating time during hot stamping on the microstructure and mechanical properties has been studied on a 5 wt.% Mn-containing steel. Heat treatments consisted of intercritical annealing at 730 °C for 1 min, followed by simulation of hot-dip galvanizing (470 °C/72 s) and then cooling to room temperature. Hot stamping simulations were performed at 700–750 °C with varying reheating times (3 and 10 min). Heat treatments were conducted at laboratory scale using a high-resolution dilatometer to monitor phase transformations, focusing on austenite reversion. Microstructural evolution was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), while hardness and micro-tensile tests evaluated mechanical performance. Samples reheated at 700 °C developed ferrite–austenite microstructures with 10–30 % retained austenite, relatively insensitive to reheating time. In contrast, reheating at 750 °C resulted in martensitic structures. The 700 °C samples achieved UTS of 1265–1320 MPa, which increased with reheating time but showed reduced elongation, while 750 °C samples achieved UTS of ~1620–1700 MPa, with minimal dependence on reheating times.

1 Introduction

In recent years, increasingly stringent regulations targeting fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions have driven the automotive industry towards the development of lightweight yet high-strength structural components, while ensuring passenger safety [1–5]. Steels remain the backbone of automotive engineering [6, 7], and significant advances have been made in this field, in particular with the development of the third-generation advanced high-strength steels (3G-AHSS), that offer

an optimized combination of strength, ductility, and cost-effectiveness, positioning them as key materials for next-generation lightweight vehicles [8, 9].

Medium-manganese steels (MMnS), containing approximately 3–12 wt.% Mn, are currently attracting significant interest due to their superior strength, ductility, and excellent formability, as well as their lower production costs compared with second-generation AHSS and conventional press-hardening steels [10]. This cost advantage primarily results from a substantial reduction in the critical transformation temperatures [11]. Typical mechanical properties include ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of 0.8–2 GPa, total elongation (TE) up to ~80% [12], resulting in extremely high product of strength and elongation (PSE). MMnS generally exhibit duplex or triplex microstructures composed of (i) α/α' (ii) γ (typically 5–30 vol.%) [13], showing transformation induced plasticity (TRIP) and/or twinning induced plasticity (TWIP) effects during deformation [1], and therefore, enhancing the mechanical response. The development of MMnS requires a comprehensive understanding of alloying effects, thermomechanical processing and microstructure–property relationships [14]. Stabilizing a sufficient volume fraction of retained austenite with controlled mechanical stability is particularly crucial. Research on heat treatments focused mainly on single intercritical annealing based on the austenite reversion concept [15–17], examining the influence of annealing temperature [18, 19] and time [20], and heating/cooling rates [21]. More recently, double annealing (or double soaking) has been shown to markedly improve the mechanical performance of medium-Mn steels [22].

Double annealing involves a second intercritical soaking step aimed at increasing both the amount and the stability of austenite. This second step may be conducted at either lower or higher temperatures compared to the first annealing stage, and typically results in a microstructure comprising a small fraction of α along with a finely dispersed mixture of martensite and austenite [23]. The first intercritical soaking promotes substantial stabilization of austenite through carbon and manganese partitioning. However, depending on the soaking temperature and degree of reversion, athermal martensite may still form during subsequent cooling, negatively affecting mechanical performance [24]. The second annealing step mitigates this effect by partially tempering the previously formed martensite and by promoting additional austenite reversion, while preserving the austenite generated during the first step. Nonetheless, when the second annealing temperature is high, a fraction of the newly reverted austenite may again transform into martensite during cooling. Consequently, the final microstructure after double annealing typically contains a small amount of α and a mixture of fresh martensite and finely dispersed γ . The martensite exhibits two distinct morphologies: i) lath-type, and ii) ultrafine non-etching blocks due to different levels of C and Mn partitioning that arise from the double soaking treatment [25]. Regions with lower carbon and manganese content tend to transform into high-temperature martensite (α'_1), while enriched regions transform into low-temperature martensite (α'_2), the latter being significantly harder due to its higher solute content. An excessive fraction of hard martensite, however, can degrade mechanical behaviour by acting as sites for stress localization and crack initiation. Similarly, also austenite exhibits bimodal distribution [23], which positively affect the mechanical response [26], accelerating the Lüders bands propagation and the suppressing local plastic instability.

Xu et al. [27] demonstrated that double annealing results in higher Mn and C enrichment, and the coexistence of coarse and ultrafine austenite, yielding a 27% increase in tensile strength (from 752 to 954 MPa) while maintaining adequate ductility (from 52.7% to 39.2%). Additional optimization

results from the introduction of Mn-gradient austenite grains and the formation of θ -carbides (cementite) during intermediate tempering, which serve as nucleation sites during subsequent austenite reversion [28]. The presence of a bimodal austenitic structure can activate deformation mechanisms beyond the TRIP effect, because ultrafine austenite (grains smaller than 10 μm) promotes a shift from the TRIP to the TWIP mechanism [29]. The microstructural evolution during double annealing is strongly influenced by the overall set of heat treatment parameters, and especially by the duration of the second soaking step. Shorter soaking will result in coarser grains and lower hardness, and may significantly alter the final microstructure and the distribution of the microstructural constituents. During longer soaking the volume fraction of reverted austenite increases and Mn and C redistribute [30], leading to a lower stability of austenite.

Given the intended application of MMnS in the automotive sector, it is essential to evaluate the compatibility with industrial routes, since the second annealing stage might be integrated with hot stamping [31]. Therefore, the present work aims to investigate the microstructural evolution and mechanical behaviour of a double-annealed MMnS, with particular attention to second annealing time, which can be construed as reheating time during hot stamping.

2 Material and methods

The material investigated in this study is a cold-rolled low-carbon, 5 wt.% Mn containing steel. The main critical transformation temperatures (austenite start and finish temperatures during heating and martensite start temperature, A_{c1} , A_{c3} and M_s respectively) of the cold-rolled steel were determined by means of high-resolution dilatometry (Bahr 805A, TA Instruments, Hull, Germany), equal to 690, 825 and 325 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively. Based on the experimental A_{c1} and A_{c3} , a first intercritical annealing treatment was performed at 730 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 64 s, followed by cooling to 470 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and an isothermal hold at that temperature for 72 s, before cooling to room temperature (Figure 1). The isothermal holding step at 470 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ simulates the hot-dip galvanizing (GI) stage in a continuous annealing line. This entire process simulates continuous annealing (CA), and samples treated by this route are denoted CA-730. A second intercritical annealing, which is analogous to a hot stamping thermal cycle, was subsequently conducted at 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 750 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 and 10 min, yielding samples designated as CA-730-700(X) and CA-730-750(X), where X is equal to 3 and 10 min, respectively, to simulate the hot stamping stage (Figure 1). All the heat treatments were carried out in a dilatometer to track the phase transformations.

Microstructural characterization of the heat-treated samples was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were prepared using standard metallographic procedures, including grinding, followed by polishing up to 1 μm diamond suspensions. A 3% Nital solution was used for etching, and repeated etching–polishing cycles were conducted to remove mechanically induced deformation layers, thereby improving microstructural contrast and eliminating deformation-induced martensite formed via the TRIP effect. All observations were made on the RD–ND (rolling direction–normal direction) plane.

Retained austenite (V_{γ}) and ferrite/martensite (V_{α}) volume fractions were quantified through X-ray diffraction (XRD). Measurements were carried out in θ – 2θ mode over 35–135 $^{\circ}$ (2θ), with a step size

of 0.015° and 2 s counting time per step, under 40 kV voltage and 30 mA current. Prior to XRD analysis, samples were polished using OP-U silica suspension with a particle size of 40 nm. Phase quantification was performed by Rietveld refinement using TOPAS v4.2 (Bruker AXS) software, while the carbon content in austenite (C_γ) was estimated from the refined lattice parameters using the empirical relation from literature [32, 33].

Vickers microhardness measurements were carried out using a 1 kg load (HV1). Dog-bone tensile specimens were machined via wire electrical discharge machining (EDM) from dilatometric samples, with a gauge length of 2.5 mm (parallel length 4 mm) and a width of 2 mm. Tensile tests were performed at a quasi-static strain rate of $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ using a 10 kN ZwickRoell testing machine, with strain measurement using a laser extensometer.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the double annealing treatment adopted in this study. The 1st and 2nd annealing steps are analogous to the continuous annealing at the steelmaker and hot stamping at the automaker, respectively.

3 Results and discussion

The dilatometric analysis performed during the first annealing stage (Figure 2a) reveals that, upon heating, the specimen exhibited a nearly linear thermal expansion at 300 °C, with slight deviations in slope attributable to variations in the applied heating rate, reproducing an industrial process condition. Around 690 °C, the rate of the increase in the relative change in length (RCL) began to decrease due to the austenite reversion process, that counters the natural expansion occurring during heating. During soaking at 730 °C, the specimen exhibited a continuous contraction caused by the austenite reversion and growth, developing a microstructure which is a mixture of α and γ (no incubation time of the transformation detected). The absence of a plateau within the 64 s holding period implies that the austenite reversion process remains incomplete (no equilibrium attained). Upon cooling to the galvanizing temperature (470 °C), the specimen showed linear contraction without any discernible phase transformation, and only a minor expansion was detected at the beginning of the isothermal holding, which is attributed to experimental noise and system stabilization. During subsequent cooling, no transformation occurred until approximately 83 °C, where martensitic transformation was observed, suggesting insufficient stabilization of austenite due to less abundant C and Mn enrichment. This results in a final microstructure consisting of α and γ/α' islands (Figure 3), with some dispersed undissolved cementite. Concerning the second annealing treatment (Figure 2b-g), after a linear expansion during heating, the increasing rate of RCL again decreased due to the reversion of the previously formed martensite into austenite, with the onset anticipated due to the

development of local compositional inhomogeneities, developed due to the Mn and C partitioning during the first austenite reversion, and the presence of remaining austenite from the first annealing treatment. Irrespective of the second annealing temperature, the material continuously contracted during the isothermal soaking; however, only after annealing for 10 min at 750 °C a plateau was reached. Finally, during final cooling to room temperature, the specimens treated at 700 °C exhibited linear contraction indicating that no phase transformation occurred. Therefore, after 3- and 10-min soaking, the microstructure consists of a mixture of γ and α (Figure 3 and Table 1). On the other hand, after treatment at 750 °C, martensitic transformation occurs at 178 °C (3 min) and 206 °C (10 min). This is confirmed by XRD, that revealed the presence of two body centred cubic phases, characterized by different tetragonalities, and the increase in the hardness value (Table 1). Such behaviour is related to the fact that at 700 °C, the amount of the developed austenite, during reversion, is smaller than that developed at 750 °C, as shown by the smaller contraction (an order of magnitude). Moreover, due to the C and Mn partitioning occurring during annealing, austenite is more enriched, compared to that developed at 750 °C, and therefore characterized by higher thermal stability, which prevents the martensitic transformation at room temperature. Moreover, as the soaking time increases, at 750 °C, austenite loses stability, as confirmed by the increasing M_s . XRD results did not lead to appreciate such difference because the carbon content does not account for the local fluctuation but provides only average values (Table 1).

Figure 2: (a) Temperature vs. RCL curve recorded during the first annealing at 730 °C, (b to g) Dilatometric curves recorded during hot stamping simulations: (b, e) reheating to 700 °C and 750 °C, (c, f) isothermal soaking at 700 and 750 °C, and (d, g) cooling from 700 °C and 750 °C.

The mechanical properties are summarized in Figure 4 (tensile curves) and Table 1 (characteristic property values). It can be observed that the specimens subjected to second annealing or reheating at 750°C showed continuous yielding while the specimen treated at 700 °C exhibited yield point elongation, due to Lüders band propagation. Moreover, it can be observed that material strength increases with second annealing or reheating at 750 °C (> 1600 MPa), satisfying the mechanical requirements for anti-intrusion parts of car bodies, due to the presence of fresh martensite developed during room temperature cooling. On the other hand, second annealing or reheating at 700 °C favours ductility, making the steel suitable for energy absorbing parts, due to the higher amounts of retained austenite, that delays the instability by transforming into martensite though TRIP effect. Concerning the effect of reheating time, it can be observed that UTS generally increases with the reheating time, while the total elongation decreases. For reheating at 700 °C, this can be attributed to the higher in amount but less stable reverted austenite developed after 10 minutes that transforms at lower strain level, inducing premature fracture. Similarly, at 750 °C, the higher strength and concomitant reduced ductility is related to the higher amount of martensite developed during cooling after the development of a larger amount of unstable reverted austenite after soaking for 10 minutes.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs showing the microstructures after first (730 °C) and second annealing at 700 and 750 °C for 3 and 10 minutes.

Table 1: XRD Results (retained austenite (V_γ), martensite (V_{α'}) and ferrite (V_α) volume fractions in % (±3%); austenite (C_γ), martensite (C_{α'}) and ferrite (C_α) carbon contents (mass content in %, ±0.02%), hardness values and tensile properties (yield strength (YS), tensile strength (UTS, MPa), uniform (UE, %) and total elongation (TE, %) measured on the heat-treated specimens.

Sample	V _γ	V _{α'}	V _α	C _γ	C _{α'}	C _α	HV1	YS	UTS	UE	TE
CA 730	23	77	-	0.29	0.04	0.03	428±17	631±3	1454±22	10.0±0.5	11.5±0.9
CA 730 700 (3)	32	68	-	0.34	0.06	0.03	417±21	647±11	1265±21	19.5±0.3	37.6±4.1
CA 730 700 (10)	36	64	-	0.31	0.05	0.03	455±24	572±6	1320±5	15.4±0.2	32.0±0.2
CA 730 750 (3)	13	24	63	0.21	0.18	0.03	468±4	911±92	1617±14	12.1±0.1	13.3±0.2
CA 730 750 (10)	12	28	60	0.21	0.17	0.03	497±15	1102±144	1701±01	8.4±0.1	10.4±1.5

Figure 4: Tensile behaviour of the single annealed (CA-730) and double annealed or hot stamped (CA-730-700 and CA-730-750) specimens soaked for 3 and 10 minutes.

4 Conclusion

The effect of double-annealing, which is analogous to hot stamping, and soaking time on the microstructure and mechanical properties of a steel containing 5 wt.% Mn was investigated. Reheating at 700 °C stabilizes more reverted austenite at room temperature, leading to maximum ductility. However, reheating at 750 °C was found to be less effective in stabilizing austenite, resulting in the presence of martensite in the final microstructure, which maximizes the tensile strength at the expense of ductility. Soaking for 3 minutes, irrespective to the reheating temperature, provides the best combination of mechanical properties due to the maximum mechanical stability of retained austenite.

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